

Enhancing Tourism Development through National Traditional Culture - Case Study of Prince Kung's Mansion

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ABSTRACT: Using Prince Kung's Mansion as a case study, this paper examines the significance of national traditional culture in the advancement of tourism, as well as its corresponding modes and effectiveness. Through interviews, surveys, and on-site visits, the authors discovered that Prince Kung's Mansion effectively merged traditional culture with tourism by utilizing digital technology to bring historical scenes to life, creating immersive cultural experiences, introducing a range of cultural and creative products, and establishing a comprehensive research and travel system. This study analyzes the successful practices of Prince Kung's Mansion and suggests several strategies, including establishing a cultural gene database for a deeper exploration of cultural significance, utilizing technological innovations to enhance interactive experiences, implementing a dual-wheel drive system combining culture and services, establishing a broad communication network, and enhancing the evaluation mechanism for cultural and tourism integration. The findings of this research can serve as a valuable reference for the development of tourism at other cultural heritage sites, particularly in terms of balancing commercial growth and the preservation of cultural authenticity, and creating a shared cultural space for both hosts and visitors.

KEY WORDS: ethnic traditional culture; tourism; development modes; Prince Kung's Mansion

1. INTRODUCTION

With the rise of cultural tourism, how to organically integrate ethnic traditional culture with the tourism industry has become a hot research topic. As the most well-preserved prince's mansion complex in Qing Dynasty in China, the Prince Kung's Mansion is rich in ethnic traditional cultural elements and has accumulated valuable experience in the development of cultural tourism. The paper takes the Prince Kung's Mansion as an example and, through questionnaire surveys and on-site investigations, deeply analyzes the model of how traditional culture promotes the development of the tourism industry, aiming to provide references for the tourism development of other cultural heritage sites. The research adopts a combination of literature analysis, questionnaire surveys, and on-site investigations to comprehensively understand the current tourism development status and visitor experiences of the Prince Kung's Mansion.

2. THE ETHNIC TRADITIONAL CULTURAL RESOURCES OF THE PRINCE KUNG'S MANSION

The Prince Kung's Mansion was first built in 1776 and is the largest and best-preserved princely residence in Qing Dynasty in China. It is not only an outstanding representative of Qing Dynasty princely architecture but also a microcosm of traditional Chinese culture. The architectural layout of the Prince Kung's Mansion embodies the essence of traditional Chinese architecture, and its garden art integrates the features of both northern and southern gardens, making it a model of classical Chinese gardens. The mansion houses

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a large number of precious cultural relics and artworks, such as paintings and calligraphy, ceramics, and furniture, which showcase the lifestyle and aesthetic tastes of the nobility in Qing Dynasty .

In addition, the Prince Kung's Mansion is rich in historical and cultural connotations. It was once the residence of many important historical figures in the Qing Dynasty and witnessed the historical process of the Qing Dynasty's decline from prosperity. The architectural decorations, couplets and plaques within the mansion all carry profound cultural implications, reflecting traditional Chinese philosophical thoughts and aesthetic concepts. These abundant traditional cultural resources of the nation have laid a solid foundation for the development of cultural tourism in the Prince Kung's Mansion.

Prince Kung's Mansion, also known as the "Wan Fu Garden," is renowned as the auspicious land of Beijing. The architectural design and landscaping of Prince Kung's Mansion feature a multitude of bat motifs in various forms, both abstract and figurative. These bats can be seen in wooden carvings on the porch, balcony stools, doors, and windows, as well as painted on the beam squares. Additionally, symbol of lucky and bat patterns adorn the wooden rafters, while bat-shaped structures can be found in the pool and buildings². In traditional Chinese culture, bats are homophonous with the word for "blessing" (fu 福), symbolizing boundless blessings and prosperity bestowed from Tian (天).

picture 1: tablet of the character fu

picture 2: symbols of different parts of the character fu

Of particular significance is the tablet of the character fu (see picture 1) within the royal palace, representing the pinnacle of fu culture in the imperial residence. The character fu incorporates five distinct Chinese characters see (picture 2), encapsulating the best wishes and pursuits in life. The lower left part of the character resembles the character for "son (子)," signifying lineage extension and population prosperity. The left side resembles the character for "talent (才)," symbolizing intellectual prowess, while the lower right side represents "field (田)," symbolizing agricultural abundance and wealth. The unsealed nature of the character for "field" denotes boundless land and limitless financial resources. The upper right part resembles the character for "many (多)," suggesting that the more blessings obtained, the better. The whole right part looks like "longevity (寿)," implying peace and long life. Taken as a whole, the character conveys the meaning of "many sons, many talents, many fields, long life, and abundant blessings."³

Chinese traditional blessing culture holds a significant position within Chinese culture, embodying thousands of years of heritage and profound significance. The concept of "blessing" encompasses all that is good and auspicious in the world, symbolizing the simplest desires and aspirations of individuals. Blessings carry a rich connotation, encompassing happiness, prosperity, health,

² Zhang (2023)

³ Zhao (2017)

longevity, abundance, family, beauty, harmony between man and nature, and peace of mind. This culture permeates various facets of Chinese society, including literature, art, religion, and folklore, reflecting the ethical values of the Chinese people.

3. CURRENT MODES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN PRINCE KUNG'S MANSION

Incorporation of Cultural Symbols and Experience Design

The fu culture, a significant aspect of traditional Chinese culture symbolizing happiness, auspiciousness, and prosperity, can be integrated into tourism cultural and creative products at Kung's Mansion through architectural elements, decorations, and other design features. This integration effectively enhances the cultural experience of tourists.

Emotional Connection

Emotions play a crucial role in enhancing tourists' satisfaction, according to the tourism experience theory⁴. By incorporating the fu culture within Prince Kung's Mansion and engaging tourists through interactive activities like explanations and performances, emotional connections can be established, thereby increasing tourists' sense of belonging and identity to the destination.

Immersive Experiences

The introduction of immersive activities related to fu culture, such as cultural festivals and fu calligraphy experiences, within Prince Kung's Mansion, allows tourists to deeply engage with traditional culture, enhancing the uniqueness of their trip.

Storytelling

By means of narrative theory to recount historical stories and legends associated with "fu" culture, tourists' attention can be captivated, enriching their cultural understanding, and elevating the overall depth of their tourism experience.

Engaging the Community

Fu culture may encourage local communities to involve in tourism activities, such as handicraft experiences, traditional food displays, and other projects, thus the tourists are transformed from mere observers to active participants in cultural exchange. This approach enhances the interactive and participatory nature of tourism, ultimately enriching the overall experience for visitors.

4. RESEARCH ON ENHANCING TOURISM DEVELOPMENT THROUGH NATIONAL TRADITIONAL CULTURE

4.1 Theory of tourism experience

The Theory of tourism experience was introduced by Thomas Cook in the 1970s with the aim of examining the process and quality of tourists' experiences. According to this theory, the experience of tourists is an active process where they must perceive, recognize, and evaluate tourism products based on their own interests, motivations, expectations, and backgrounds. Additionally, the quality of tourism experiences is influenced by various factors such as the appeal of tourist attractions, the quality of tourism services, and the psychological state of tourists.

4.2 Case Study

Based on the theory of tourism experience, Prince Kung's Mansion is selected as the focal point for a detailed examination. The study delves into the development modes, strategies and marketing tactics employed by the tourist attraction through observation, questionnaire and interviews. By gathering data from various sources, the research aims to provide a thorough analysis of the current development status and approach of Prince Kung's Mansion.

- Observation of tourist behavior:

⁴ Long (2010)

Direct observations were made on the behavior of tourists and their utilization of tourism facilities within Prince Kung's Mansion. First-hand information was obtained, revealing that tourists followed fixed tour routes within the estate, with large crowds congregating in areas such as the back garden, bat pond, and the tablet of the character fu, where they tended to linger.

- Questionnaire:

Amid the escalating popularity of cultural tourism in the market, Prince Kung's Mansion stands out as a prominent example of palace architecture in Qing Dynasty, brimming with historical and cultural significance. To further explore the potential for integrating traditional culture with tourism, a comprehensive questionnaire was conducted to gauge tourists' perceptions and preferences towards Prince Kung's Mansion and its cultural and creative products. The questionnaire comprised 15 items focusing on aspects such as visitors' interest in national culture, familiarity with cultural products, purchasing intentions, quality assessments, pricing perceptions, and areas for improvement. This questionnaire was designed to provide insights into tourists' attitudes towards the fusion of traditional culture with tourism, aiding in steering the future development of cultural tourism.

The questionnaire targeted four distinct groups of individuals - students, office workers, freelancers, and retirees - each representing varying travel preferences and interests in cultural experiences. These groups were selected to capture a diverse range of perspectives essential for the survey.

A total of 280 questionnaires were distributed through onsite interviews at the scenic spot and online research, resulting in a 100% retrieval rate. The data collected was analyzed alongside published literature and reports to offer recommendations for the enrichment of national traditional culture and tourism development.

- In-depth interview:

Structured interviews with tourism professionals at Prince Kung's Mansion were conducted to gather detailed insights and perspectives, aiding in exploratory research to grasp industry insights, visitor experiences, and preferences.

- Content analysis:

A systematic examination of various materials such as travel reviews, social media content, and tourism promotions was carried out to ascertain tourists' perceptions of national culture and tourist destinations. This analysis aimed to establish a clearer understanding of the consumer market and direction in alignment with the research objectives.

In the end, all the data was inputted into Excel for descriptive statistics, presenting information in numerical and percentage forms. Leveraging the SWOT analysis and questionnaire findings, the research undertook a comprehensive evaluation of the integration of traditional culture and tourism at Prince Kung's Mansion.

4.3 Data Analysis

The data analysis of Prince Kung's Mansion revealed a positive and promising trend in the effectiveness of traditional culture in promoting tourism development. A total of 280 questionnaires were distributed using a combination of online and offline methods, all of which were successfully collected and deemed valid, resulting in a 100% questionnaire efficiency rate. This ensured the accuracy and representativeness of the data.

The majority of respondents were concentrated in the Beijing area, providing valuable insights into local tourists' perspectives on traditional culture and cultural products. The results (see chart 1) indicate a strong interest in ethnic culture among tourists, with only 12.5% expressing limited interest and 87.5% showing varying degrees of interest, highlighting their admiration and appreciation for ethnic traditions.

Chart 1 degree of interest in national culture

Chart 2 revealed that Han culture was the most popular, with 45% of respondents expressing a high level of interest, showcasing the widespread recognition and fondness for Han culture among tourists.

Chart 2 the most popular ethnic traditional culture

At the same time, there has been significant interest in the Manchu minority culture, which accounts for 10% of respondents, while other minority cultures have also garnered recognition from 14.29% of respondents. This data not only demonstrates the appeal of ethnic minority cultures to tourists, but also emphasizes the importance of preserving and promoting these cultures.

Particularly noteworthy is that 71% of respondents expressed a willingness to visit tourist attractions for cultural and creative products that resonate with them. This data (chart 3) clearly indicates the considerable potential of cultural and creative products in attracting tourists and driving tourism development.

Chart 3 the readiness to visit a scenic spot for the interesting cultural and creative products

Furthermore, chart 4 shows that 66% of respondents believe that the growth of the cultural and creative industry has a positive impact on the local economy and culture, with 95% expressing optimism about the prospects of this industry.

Chart 4 degree of the impact of the cultural and creative industry on the local economy and culture

Regarding tourists’ attitudes towards the development prospects of the cultural and creative industry, Table 1 shows that they hold a significantly optimistic view, with 78.93% (very optimistic 17.5% + relatively optimistic 61.43%) of the respondents being optimistic about the future of the cultural and creative industry. However, there are still potential concerns, as 20.86% of the people hold a neutral or negative attitude (average 12.86% + not very optimistic 8%), indicating that the “pain” points in the industry's development need to be paid attention to. It can be seen that the industry has strong market confidence, but it is necessary to be vigilant about the potential problems that the “silent minority” may reflect (such as lack of innovation, excessive commercialization, etc.).

Table 1 attitude towards the future development prospects of the cultural and creative industry

options	number of people	ratio
very optimistic	49	17.50%
comparatively optimistic	172	61.43%
optimistic	36	12.86%
not optimistic	23	8%
very pessimistic	0	0

Table 2 shows the promoting power of the cultural and creative products in enhancing the travel experience of tourists who can achieve the ideal state of “traveling by immersing oneself in the scenery”, since 81.79% (17.86% strongly agree + 63.93% agree) of the respondents highly agree that cultural and creative products can improve the travel experience. However, 18.22% (11.43% somewhat disagree + 6.79% completely disagree) of the respondents still have doubts, indicating that there is a problem of insufficient integration of products and scenes. The implication is that the focus should be on developing scene-based cultural and creative products with local cultural characteristics to enhance the immersive experience.

Table 2. the promoting power of the cultural and creative products in enhancing one’s travel experience

options	number of people	ratio
strongly agree	50	17.86%
agree	179	63.93%
somewhat disagree	32	11.43%
completely disagree	19	6.79%
Total	280	100.00%

About the evaluation of the quality of the cultural and creative products in the current market, table 3 reveals that about 56.07% of the respondents are basically satisfied with them, thinking that the quality is high (very high 10.71% + high 45.36%), and the rest believe that the product quality has room for improvement. This is what is called a significant “Long Tail Effect”⁵. Regarding the price of these products, there (table 4) is shown the price sensitivity highlights: 77.5% of the people think the price is high (51.43% acceptable high + 26.07% too high), and value recognition gap: only 26.43% accept value for money, and the quality evaluation forms a cognitive separation. It can be found that the core contradiction, product quality perception and price recognition does not match, suggesting the need to reconstruct the value communication system (such as strengthening IP story-based marketing, process value visualization).

Table 3 the quality of current cultural and creative products

options	number of people	ratio
extremely high	30	10.71%
higher	127	45.36%
high	116	41.43%
lower	7	2.50%
extremely low	0	0%

⁵ Han (2024)

Table 4 the price of cultural and creative products

options	number of people	ratio
price to value	74	26.43%
acceptable price	144	51.43%
too high price	73	26.07%
too low price	19	6.79%

In addition, table 5 tells that there are many aspects that tourists think can be improved in these products. Quality first: 58.93% of the absolute top demand, confirming the quality pain points in Table 3; category innovation: 41.07% of the people require an increase in types, reflecting the problem of product homogeneity in the market; price optimization: 27.14% of the demand for price reduction corresponds to the price sensitivity in Table 4; brand building: 19.29% of the demand for promotion shows that there is still room for improvement in market recognition. So suggestions are implied in progressive improvement: quality improvement → category innovation → price adjustment → brand building, forming a progressive optimization path.

Table 5 possible improvements in cultural and creative products

options	number of people	ratio
improving quality	165	58.93%
increasing the variety	115	41.07%
lowering the price	76	27.14%
promoting brand	54	19.29%
other	13	4.64%

In summary, the data analysis of Prince Kung's Mansion highlights the positive integration of traditional culture and tourism. However, feedback from most tourists reveals dissatisfaction with high prices, poor quality, and limited variety of cultural and creative products. Therefore, it is essential to enhance market awareness, promote products effectively, and improve quality standards. Cultural and creative products serve as a vital link between traditional culture and tourism, being well-loved by tourists and playing a crucial role in driving tourism development, economic prosperity, and cultural preservation. Therefore, it is imperative for scenic spots and related institutions to increase investment in and promotion of cultural and creative products to meet the diverse needs of tourists and foster sustainable tourism development. Moreover, it is suggested to carry out further research: in-depth interview to explore the specific demands of the “general” evaluation group, analysis of competitive products to clarify the reference standards for quality improvement, and price elasticity test to determine the optimal pricing range.

5.2 SWOT PEST analysis of the traditional cultural modes of Prince Kung’s Mansion to support tourism development

5.2.1 Strengths

Regarding the political environment, Prince Kung’s Mansion, being an ancient palace complex from the Qing Dynasty, holds significant historical and cultural value. The government’s strong support for the integrated development of cultural tourism industry creates a favorable political environment for the fusion of traditional culture and tourism at Prince Kung’s Mansion. This support

ensures proper protection and utilization of Prince Kung's Mansion and other ancient structures⁶. In the economic context, the rising demand for diverse tourism experiences, especially cultural ones, due to improved living standards, presents growth opportunities for cultural tourist attractions like Prince Kung's Mansion. By hosting various cultural activities and exhibitions, the Mansion has boosted visitor participation and satisfaction. Additionally, the introduction of cultural and creative products has further enhanced the tourist experience and contributed to attracting more visitors. From a social perspective, tourists' keen interest in ethnic cultures and growing respect for cultural heritage provide a solid foundation for the sustainable development of traditional cultural sites like Prince Kung's Mansion. Increased education levels have also led to a rise in visitors to cultural attractions. In terms of technology, the integration of virtual reality and augmented reality technologies in cultural tourism offers a more immersive experience for visitors at Prince Kung's Mansion. Innovations like the science and technology pavilion and digital commemorative coin have enhanced the technological appeal of the Mansion and made its promotion more efficient through social media and internet platforms.

5.2.2 Weaknesses

Despite its rich historical and cultural significance, Prince Kung's Mansion's publicity and promotion efforts fall short of maximizing its cultural status. Enhanced investment in marketing strategies, innovative approaches, and diversified channels is necessary to increase its appeal to potential tourists. The lack of innovation in developing and marketing tourism products has hindered the Mansion's brand recognition and popularity. While cultural and creative products enjoy strong demand, some improvements, such as pricing, quality, and innovation, are needed at Prince Kung's Mansion. Furthermore, the aging infrastructure within the Palace poses a challenge, affecting visitor experience and the overall image of the site. Additional funding for maintenance and repairs is crucial to ensure a safe and comfortable environment for visitors.

5.2.3 Opportunities

National policies supporting the cultural tourism industry provide a robust foundation for the growth of traditional cultural attractions like Prince Kung's Mansion. The increasing emphasis on cultural tourism and rising disposable income among Chinese residents present new opportunities for the Mansion's development. In the first three quarters of 2024, the per capita disposable income of Chinese residents was 30,941 yuan, a significant increase from the previous data⁷. This data reflects the continuous increase of Chinese residents' income and the continuous improvement of economic conditions. The increase of residents' disposable income makes people have more idle funds to go to Prince Kung's Mansion, which provides certain opportunities for the development of tourism. As the tourism market expands and diversifies, unique cultural attractions like Prince Kung's Mansion stand to benefit from the growing demand for cultural experiences. The Mansion's historical value and cultural charm make it appealing to tourists seeking authentic cultural experiences.

5.3 Suggestions to promote national traditional culture in improving tourism

After conducting a thorough analysis of the cultural and tourism integration model implemented at Prince Kung's Mansion, and reflecting on its experience and lessons learned, it is evident that the integration of national traditional culture and tourism presents both promising opportunities and significant challenges. In order to achieve a deeper integration of culture and tourism across a wider array of ethnic regions, and to unlock the full potential and allure of the cultural tourism industry, it is essential to explore and implement the following key directions.

5.3.1 Guidance and support of government policy

The government should continue to introduce policies that support the integrated development of ethnic traditional culture and

⁶ Ma (2022)

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<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1790572332714437568&wfr=spider&for=pc&searchword=%E9%A9%AC%E5%8A%9B%20%E5%86%B0%E9%9B%AA%E6%97%85%E6%B8%B8&source=ucbrowser>

tourism. This includes increasing capital investment and offering policy support for cultural tourism projects in ethnic minority areas. For instance, establishing dedicated funds for cultural heritage preservation, tourism infrastructure development, and the creation of tourism products. Additionally, implementing favorable tax policies to incentivize enterprises to actively engage in the development of the ethnic cultural tourism industry⁸.

Emphasizing policy guidance will help streamline the tourism industry in ethnic minority areas, promoting its optimization and growth. Encouraging tourism enterprises to innovate their business models, explore new ventures such as green tourism and smart tourism, and bolster the industry's capacity for sustainable development.

5.3.2 Technology-innovation driven approaches

Leveraging emerging technologies to enhance the competitiveness and experiential value of ethnic cultural tourism is essential. For example, employing artificial intelligence technology to create intelligent tour guide systems that offer personalized travel recommendations and explanations to visitors. Integrating virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies to deliver immersive cultural experiences allows tourists to fully appreciate the richness of national culture⁹.

Utilizing big data technology to analyze tourist preferences and market trends will provide valuable insights to support tourism product development, marketing strategies, and service enhancements. For instance, by analyzing online behavioral data, businesses can effectively identify target customer demographics and tailor marketing initiatives accordingly.

5.3.3 Community engagement and collaborative development

It is crucial for empowering communities to play a central role in the development of ethnic cultural tourism. Encouraging active participation of residents in tourism management activities, such as establishing home-stays, farm shops, and handicraft stores, can help distribute the benefits of tourism development more equitably among community members.

Moreover, it will foster a sense of shared responsibility and ownership to establish collaboration mechanisms between communities, tourism enterprises, and government entities to engage in tourism planning, development, and management. By involving communities in the tourism development process, we can ensure the preservation and innovation of national culture, foster positive interactions between tourism growth and community well-being, and create a model of tourism development based on shared participation, governance, and benefits.

To sum up, the fusion of national traditional culture and tourism holds significant potential and promising prospects. By drawing inspiration from the experiences of Prince Kung's Mansion and tailoring development strategies to local contexts, different ethnic regions can leverage their cultural strengths to drive high-quality tourism growth, achieving a harmonious balance between cultural preservation and economic prosperity. Moving forward, policies, technological innovation, and community engagement will serve as the driving forces propelling the bright future of ethnic cultural tourism.

6. CONCLUSION AND INSPIRATION

6.1 Summary of Conclusions

Cultural value and tourist appeal

The cultural richness and historical significance embodied in Prince Kung's Mansion showcase profound cultural values that continue to captivate tourists, underscoring the enduring appeal of traditional national heritage in the realm of tourism. The keen interest displayed by visitors in ethnic traditions underscores the pivotal role of indigenous cultural elements as a driving force in tourism development, instilling a sense of vitality and allure in the tourism landscape.

⁸ Zhong (2023)

⁹ Shangguan (2025)

Current status of cultural and creative products

The investigation reveals that cultural and creative products hold considerable potential in attracting tourists. Nonetheless, issues such as pricing discrepancies, inconsistent quality, and limited variety impede their capacity to play a more impactful role in enhancing tourism experiences. These challenges underscore the imperative of conducting market research, enhancing product quality control, and fostering innovative design strategies to elevate the overall competitiveness of cultural and creative products.

Comprehensive analysis of cultural and tourism integration

Employing the SWOTPEST analysis framework¹⁰ sheds light on the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities associated with the integration of culture and tourism at Prince Kung's Mansion. Noteworthy strengths include policy support, robust social and cultural foundations, and technological advancements, while weaknesses encompass deficiencies in publicity, product innovation, and infrastructure maintenance. Opportunities for growth stem from policy directives, economic advancements, and evolving market demands. This comprehensive analysis offers a blueprint for grasping the intricacies of cultural and tourism integration, thereby informing strategic development initiatives aimed at fostering harmonious growth in both spheres.

6.2 Inspiration for cultural tourism development in ethnic areas

In the future, the development of cultural tourism in diverse ethnic groups and regions should delve deeper into its cultural significance, create distinctive tourism products, attract visitors, and immerse them in the cultural allure¹¹. Additionally, efforts should be made to enhance the promotion and dissemination of tourism and cultural information to increase the visibility of tourist attractions and foster the sustainable development of cultural heritage. To achieve sustainable growth, it is imperative to nurture skilled professionals and enhance the quality of tourism services. The following are specific development strategies proposed in response.

Exploring cultural significance and develop unique tourism products

Ethnic regions possess unique and abundant traditional cultural resources, such as traditional festivals, handicrafts, and folk activities of minority groups¹². These cultural elements should be explored in depth and transformed into appealing tourism products. For instance, akin to the immersive fu cultural experience activity at Prince Kung's Mansion, other regions could design experiential projects centered around their core cultural symbols, enabling visitors to actively engage and appreciate the cultural charm.

It is necessary to adapt to modern consumer demands and innovate tourism product formats and utilize digital technology to create virtual tourism experiences, allowing tourists to remotely experience the unique customs of various cultures. Tourism services can be tailored for the personalized preferences of diverse tourist groups seeking ethnic cultural experiences.

Enhancing prominence of tourist destinations through effective publicity and promotion

More publicity efforts can be devoted by means of modern marketing techniques. Social media platforms, tourism websites, online tourism communities, and other digital channels can be used to disseminate cultural tourism information widely. Craft visually appealing promotional materials can be utilized to attract a larger audience, including videos and graphics showcasing the region's natural beauty, cultural attractions, and folk traditions.

Other activities are suggested, for example, conducting themed marketing campaigns integrating national cultural characteristics to establish a strong tourism brand, hosting ethnic culture festivals and folk culture exhibitions to garner media coverage and elevate the visibility of tourist destinations, and forging partnerships with travel agencies, influencers, and bloggers to amplify destination recognition through word-of-mouth referrals and professional endorsements.

Prioritizing preservation and sustainable development of cultural heritage

¹⁰ Kong (2019)

¹¹ Luo (2021)

¹² Zhang (2023)

The focus should be on the conservation of national cultural heritage in the process of tourism development, and the plans are to be made for ensuring the authenticity, integrity, and continuity of cultural assets. For instance, repair and maintenance efforts are to be made for ancient buildings and sites significant for traditional skills transmission within ethnic minority communities to prevent deterioration due to excessive development¹³.

Other measures can be adopted, such as promoting sustainable cultural tourism development to achieve a balance between economic, social, and environmental benefits, encouraging community involvement in tourism initiatives, helping residents to reap benefits from the industry while fostering a sense of cultural stewardship, and implementing community-based tourism projects, offering visitors insights into local lifestyles and traditions to stimulate cultural preservation and community growth.

Fostering professional development and improving tourism service

Some training programs should be developed for tourism professionals in ethnic minority regions, encompassing tour guides, tourism planners, and cultural heritage preservation experts. Through academic education and vocational training, the expertise of tourism practitioners will be enhanced to effectively convey the essence of national culture¹⁴.

Also tourism services must be improved, with a focus on enhancing visitor experiences. In other words, holistic service must be ensured by improving tourism reception facilities, streamline service processes, and mechanisms for visitor feedback. For example, multilingual tour services at tourist destinations, convenient access to transportation, dining, accommodation, and other amenities to enhance overall satisfaction of tourists.

Facilitating cultural exchanges and collaborations across regions

Cultural exchange initiatives should be promoted among diverse ethnic areas, facilitating the sharing of successful cultural and tourism integration experiences. Such events as seminars and experience-sharing on ethnic cultural tourism will foster collaboration in tourism product development, promotion, and cultural preservation strategies among different regions¹⁵.

Collaboration will be desirable for improving cross-regional tourism routes, combining unique cultural tourism resources from various regions to create a more enticing tourism portfolio. Through regional partnerships, resources can be pooled, and tourists can be reciprocally directed to each other's locations, collectively advancing tourism development in ethnic regions.

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¹³ Tian (2020)

¹⁴ Luo (2021)

¹⁵ Tang (2024)

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